

pseudostems was infected and another weed, *Bracharia* sp., also was probably infected. In the Chiriqui area 200 miles west of Panama City, rice in six large rice farms did not have bacterial blight, but many colonies of the local common weed *Panicum maximum* showed blight symptoms. If isolation and inoculation experiments confirm the observed symptoms to be those of bacterial blight of rice, the original hosts of the bacterium would appear to be the weed species. Upland rice culture probably has localized the disease; in paddy rice, water is a major agent for dissemination of the bacterium. No bacterial blight was noted on rice on many farms of the Boliche and Samborondon areas of Ecuador, but *P. maximum* grew everywhere and in most places showed symptoms typical of bacterial blight. ❧

Seed-borne infection and ufra disease

Tin Sein, Plant Pathology Department, Agricultural Research Institute, Rangoon, Burma

Seth observed *Ditylenchus angustus*, the nematode pathogen of ufra disease, in rice grains. Hashioka sprayed a suspension of nematodes in water onto rice seeds but the seeds did not produce diseased plants.

Studies in Burma showed that heavily infested plants produced very little seed; the panicles contained many unfilled grains. Microscopic examination showed the presence of about 15.4 nematodes in each unfilled "grain" and 5.3 in one mature grain. One mature seed carried too little inoculum to cause disease. However, large numbers of seed grown together resulted in disease when naturally infected seeds were used as the source of inoculum. ❧

Testing some pesticides against ufra disease

Tin Sein, Plant Pathology Department, Agricultural Research Institute, Rangoon, Burma

Preliminary tests showed 4 of 47 pesticides were significantly better than a check spraying in increasing the rice

yield in pots infested with the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, which causes ufra disease. The 4 pesticides were compared for effectiveness in further tests.

Ten heavily infested C4-63 rice plants, each in 1-kg soil in a 25-cm-diameter pot with 3 cm of water above the soil, were sprayed 3 times at weekly intervals with each pesticide suspension (33 ml, 0.21% ai.), or 0.07 g a.i. of carbofuran granules was sprinkled on the soil 3 times. One control was included with diseased plants and one with healthy plants. Four weeks after spraying, the average number of fertile tillers per pot for the various treatments were: healthy control, 6; diseased control, sprayed with water, 0; with monocrotophos, 1.8; with phenazine, 2.3; with parathion, 2.4; with carbofuran,

4.6. LSD at the 1% level was 1,702.

In another pot test of varied dosages of carbofuran granules (3% a.i.), the density of nematodes was determined by soaking 1-cm-long shoot sections, counting the nematodes in the soaking water, and calculating the number that would have been found in 1 g of shoot. There were 10 replications. With carbofuran applications of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 g/pot, the numbers of nematodes found were 238.9, 96.0, 84.6, 34.1, 18.4, and 17.7, respectively. L.D. 50, calculated according to Bliss, was found to be 0.9825 g granules per pot. Assuming 1 M kg to be the weight of 1 ha of soil 15 cm deep, L.D. 50 is about 1,000 kg/ha of carbofuran granules.

The pesticides may not be economical for use against ufra disease of rice. ❧

Pest management and control

INSECTS

A new lepidopterous pest of rice

Lourdes A. Malabayoc, research assistant, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

A hairy, greenish caterpillar about 20 mm long when full grown has been observed attacking rice plants. Unchecked populations can increase rapidly and cause severe defoliation (see figure). The pest was first observed in a screenhouse at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) in December 1975, and later on the IRRI farm. The same insect had been reported damaging rice plants at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in Nueva Ecija, Philippines, in September 1971, and in Pangasinan, Philippines. A. G. Hayes at the British Museum of Natural History identified specimens as near *Rivula atimeta* Swinhoe, 1905.

The adult moth is slightly larger than the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*. It is cream colored with a tinge of very light brown at the edge of the forewings. The abdomen of the female is greenish due to the presence of eggs.

Rice plants show defoliation caused by a hairy, greenish caterpillar in IRRI Screenhouse.